

A Preventable Case of Myoclonus

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ABSTRACT

Gabapentin is a very commonly used medication for neuropathic symptoms. Gabapentin is solely excreted by the kidneys and it is of prime importance that the dose of the gabapentin be adjusted according to the creatinine clearance. We present a case of gabapentin induced myoclonus in a patient with chronic kidney disease.

Keywords: Myoclonus; Gabapentin; Hypertension

INTRODUCTION

Gabapentin is approved by the FDA for treating seizure disorders and neuropathic pain but has been frequently used as an off-label medication to treat fibromyalgia, alcohol dependence/withdrawal, moderate to severe vasomotor menopausal symptoms, essential tremors, generalized anxiety disorders, intractable hiccups, chronic pruritus, restless leg syndrome. Gabapentin acts by blocking voltage dependent calcium channels and by modulating excitatory neurotransmitter release. The appropriate dosing based on the patient's creatinine clearance is very important to prevent the adverse side effects/toxicity of gabapentin.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 67 year old patient with a past medical history significant for Hypertension, Diabetes, stage 3 chronic kidney disease with an eGFR value of 45, Diabetic neuropathy which has been well controlled with gabapentin 300 mg TID presents to the clinic with a 3 day history of worsening jerking and twitching of the head, trunk and all the four extremities. The [Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour \(ICMCJR\) 2024 | Volume 3 | Issue 5](#)

patient also experienced intractable hiccups. The movements were unintentional and extremely disabling causing impairment in the patient's activities of daily living. There was no history of any seizure-like activity. No history of any presyncopal or syncopal episodes that were reported. There was no reported change in the patient's mental status. The patient does not have any history of recreational drug use. There is no history of any smoking or alcohol use as well. The patient had failed to follow-up with the PCP and was not seen in the clinic for longitudinal care for the last 6 months. The patient however got a refill on his medications per the clinic medication refill protocol.

The patient's medications included lisinopril, dapagliflozin, gabapentin. Vital signs were within normal limits. The patient had a BMI of 30.2.

Pertinent physical findings were significant for twitching of the perioral muscles and hyperkinetic repetitive jerky movements involving the bilateral upper and lower extremities with prominence to the upper extremities. The patient also had persistent hiccups. Otherwise the rest of the physical exam including a complete neurologic exam was within normal limits.

Stat labs ordered on the patient were within acceptable range except worsening of the patient's chronic kidney disease. There was a bump in the serum creatinine from the patient's usual baseline of 1.7 mg/dl to a value of 2.7 mg/dl. Estimated GFR also decreased from the patient's baseline of 45 to 23. Blood urea nitrogen was 25. CT head was within normal limits.

The patient was diagnosed with Myoclonus secondary to gabapentin toxicity resulting from worsening chronic kidney disease. Gabapentin was discontinued immediately and the patient's symptoms resolved within the next 3 days.

DISCUSSION

Gabapentin is a very common drug used to treat neuropathic pain and seizures and also has a multitude of off-label use including but not limited to fibromyalgia, alcohol dependence/withdrawal, moderate to severe vasomotor menopausal symptoms, essential tremors, generalized anxiety disorders, intractable hiccups, chronic pruritus, restless leg syndrome. Gabapentin is structurally related to GABA but it does not bind to GABA-a or GABA-b receptors. Gabapentin modulates the release of excitatory neurotransmitters which participate in epileptogenesis and nociception^[1].

Elderly individuals pose a higher risk of developing gabapentin induced myoclonic activity irrespective of the renal function^[2]. The incidence of gabapentin related myoclonus in end stage renal disease is high. The clearance of gabapentin is impaired in end stage renal disease which causes toxic accumulation of the drug leading to myoclonus^[3]. The recommended dose and frequency adjusted for creatinine clearance is as follows^[4]

Creatinine clearance greater than 79: No adjustment necessary-not to exceed 3600 mg per day in 3 divided doses

Creatinine clearance 50-79: No adjustment necessary, not to exceed 1800 mg per day in 3 divided doses

Creatinine clearance 30-49: 50% reduction- not to exceed 900 mg per day in 2-3 divided doses

Creatinine clearance 15-29: 75% reduction-not to exceed 600 mg per day in 1-2 divided doses

Creatinine clearance less than 15: 90% reduction-not to exceed 300 mg per day in 1 dose

This case report highlights the importance of closely monitoring renal function prior to automatically refilling drugs primarily excreted by the kidney. Clinicians should be aware of the potential harms resulting from automatic refills of medications.

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